

ENSURING SAFETY OF LIGHT INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTS BASED ON TECHNICAL REGULATIONS

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Abstract: *The article addresses the issues of safety of light industry products on the basis of technical regulations and analyzes the standard requirements for the safety of light industry products.*

Keywords: *Technical regulation, light industry, safety, standard requirements, biological and chemical safety.*

Testing of light industry products is carried out in accordance with the General Technical Regulation "On safety of light industry products", adopted by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 11, 2016 No 148.

The technical regulation establishes safety requirements for light industry products and applies to the following types of products:

- Raw silk;
- silk wool;
- yarn (cotton yarn, blend, wool, silk);
- Textiles, knitted and non-woven fabrics (linen, clothes, towels, decorative, furniture, fur);
- garments from textile materials;
- hosiery products;
- carpets and upholstery from felt, non-woven and textile materials;
- hats (knitted, woven and faux fur);
- Textile and perfumery products.

The requirements of the technical regulation do not apply to medical functions, arts and crafts, souvenirs, products and products manufactured to the specific requirements of the customer.

This technical regulation establishes the following requirements for safety of light industry products:

- biological safety;
- mechanical safety;

- chemical safety;
- electrical safety;
- environmental safety;
- industrial and production safety;
- ensuring uniformity of measurements and test methods.

Analysis and Results

The technical regulation may establish other requirements for ensuring the safety of light industry products.

Technical regulations on safety of light industry products include:

- safety descriptions of products and services;
- A complete list of products for which safety requirements are established;
- requirements for terms, packaging, stamps or labels, as well as the rules of their representation and product identification;
- Procedure for state control;
- Rules required to assess the compliance of products with the requirements of regulatory documents in the field of technical regulation.

Technical regulations should not contain requirements for the design and execution of the product, except in cases where the safety of the product is not ensured due to the lack of requirements for the design and execution of the product, taking into account the level of risk to human life and health.

This technical regulation is complete, is valid throughout the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan and can be amended only by making changes and additions in the prescribed manner. Formation of programs for the development of technical regulations is carried out by the Uzbek Agency for Standardization, Metrology and Certification, taking into account the proposals of other competent state bodies in the field of technical regulation and state and economic management bodies within their competence.

Programs for the development of technical regulations are approved by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan and published in the prescribed manner. State control over compliance with technical regulations is carried out by officials of the authorized state bodies and public administration bodies in the field of technical regulation in the manner prescribed by law.

In accordance with the resolution, the general technical regulation "On safety of light industry products" approved normative documents on standardization, defining the test methods of regulated facilities.

The technical regulation establishes safety requirements for light industry products and includes raw silk, silk wool (shyolkovaya vata), kalava (cotton yarn, blended, wool, silk), textile, knitted and non-woven

fabrics (sheets, clothes, towels, decorative, furniture, fur), textile garments, hosiery, felt, non-woven and textile carpets and upholstery, hats, refers to textile and perfumery products.

For the production of products in accordance with the requirements of regulatory documents in the framework of technical regulations and the use of raw materials and supplies. The production process must comply with the requirements of technical regulations and technical documentation.

The manufacturer of the product must be able to control the implementation of the technological process to ensure its safety. The electrical specific surface resistance of upholstery and carpet products shall not exceed 10^{14} Ohms. The specific weight of free sulfuric acid in felt products should not exceed 0.7%.

The safety of light industry products is assessed by the following biological and chemical safety:

1. Biological properties (hygroscopicity, air permeability, water tightness, specific surface electrical resistance, electrostatic field strength, toxicity index);

2. Chemical composition (release of harmful chemicals into the air and (or) water as much as possible);

Biological safety indicators of light industry products must comply with the requirements of technical regulations.

Product labeling requirements. The product label must be reliable, readable, and easy to see and identify. To mark the finished product:

- Product label;
- Ribbon with the image of the product brand;
- glue;
- control tape.

The mark used on the product, its place of affixing and installation must comply with the requirements of this technical regulation. The label must contain the following mandatory information:

- Product name;
- name of the country of origin;
- the name of the manufacturer or a representative appointed by the seller / manufacturer;
- legal address of the manufacturer or a representative appointed by the seller / manufacturer;
- composition of raw materials;
- trademark (if any);
- manufacturer's warranty obligations (if applicable);
- date of manufacture;
- batch number of the product (if necessary);

- environmental safety sign (if necessary);
- product storage mark;

The first, second and third floor clothing labels must contain the following additional information:

- Appearance and mass fraction (%) of natural and chemical raw materials in the material of surface and lining products. The error Q from the actual composition of the raw material should not exceed 5%.

- Product size.

Knitted and woven fabrics, their products, curtains must contain the following additional information:

- Mass of one piece at normal humidity (for knitted fabrics);
- type of paint (if any).

Machine-made upholstery and carpets must have the following additional information:

- Article number;
- product size;
- coating length;
- photo and color number;
- mass fraction of appearance and index (in%). The error Q from the actual composition of the raw material should not exceed 5%.

Products made of natural fibers and hats with up to 5% chemical fiber contain the name of natural raw materials without percentages. Markings and information must be provided in the state language. For imported products, the country of manufacture, the name of the manufacturer and its legal address may be given in the Latin alphabet.

Conclusions

The use of environmentally friendly and similar words is not allowed without proper instructions confirming environmental safety. If necessary, additional information on the use of textiles can be provided. The methods of use of products made of textile materials are clearly indicated on the label, which is made of durable material that is resistant to moisture and heat and can be stored for as long as the main fabric of the garment.

REFERENCES:

1. General technical regulation "On safety of light industry products" adopted by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 11, 2016 No. 148.
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3. Regulation "On the procedure for adoption and application of international, interstate, regional standards and standards of foreign countries in the Republic", approved by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 14, 2019 No 220.

4. <https://standart.uz/>